

Colorimetric and Conductometric Study of the Reaction between Fe(III) and 2-Propionyl-1-Naphthol Oxime (2-Pronapox) in Aqueous-Ethanol Medium.*

D. N. Patkar and R. N. Merchant

Fe³⁺ ion forms a green coloured complex with 2-PRONAPOX in weakly acidic medium, which is soluble in ethanol-water mixture containing 50% or more ethanol. The pH range of constant absorbance is 2.9–3.2. The complex shows maximum absorbance at 660–670 m μ . The composition of the complex, established by colorimetric and conductometric methods is 1 : 1.

Fe³⁺ ion forms a green complex with 2-PRONAPOX¹ in the pH range 2.2–4v soluble in 60% ethanol and having maximum absorbance at 660–670 m μ where absorbance due to reagent is negligible. Absorbance is constant at pH 2.9–3.2 and at temperature 28°–45°. Beer's law is obeyed from 12 to 40 μ g of Fe³⁺ per ml. Study of the composition of the complex in 60% ethanol by Yoe and Jones's mole ratio method indicated considerable dissociation of complex. The method of extrapolation could not, therefore, be applied.

The authors have determined the composition of the Fe³⁺ complex formed under the conditions stated from colorimetric measurements using the modified mole ratio method of Harvey and Manning³, the method of limiting slope⁴, the slope ratio method³ and Job's method of continuous variation⁵. The composition has also been confirmed by conductometric studies using the monovariation method⁶.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals : A.R. Fe₂(SO₄)₃, (NH₄)₂SO₄, 24 H₂O was employed to prepare Fe³⁺ solution and a solution containing about 1 mg/ml of Fe³⁺ was standardised by the oxide method and also by the volumetric method. H₂SO₄, NH₄NO₃ used were of A.R. grade.

Reagent : Reagent was prepared by the method described earlier⁷. Solutions of the reagent were prepared in double distilled ethanol.

* Paper read at the 5th Annual Convention of Indian Chemical Society held at Roorkee, November 1967.

1. N. D. Tambat and R. N. Merchant, *Jour. Univ. Bom.*, 1968, **45** (vi), 517.
2. J. H. Yoe and A. L. Lones, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 114.
3. A. E. Harvey and D. L. Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
4. H. E. Bent and French, *ibid.*, 1941, **63**, 538.
5. P. Job, *Anal. Chim.*, 1928, **9**, 113.
6. Nayar and Pande, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1948, **27A**, 284.
7. N. D. Tambat and R. N. Merchant, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 13.

Instruments : Spectrophotometric measurements were made on a Beckmann DU spectrophotometer with cells having light path 1 cm. For all other colorimetric studies a Hilger Biochem Absorptiometer (C-100 type) was used. An Elico LI-10 pH-meter was used for pH measurements. Conductometric measurements were made using a Toshniwal (CL 01/02 Sr. No. 0117) conductivity bridge at $26^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$.

Spectral Studies and Nature of the Complex : To study the nature of the complex by the method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁸, Fe^{3+} ($7.16 \times 10^{-4} M$) and reagent solutions were taken in the molar ratios 1 : 0.5, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and absorbance at pH 3 and at ionic strength 0.6 (NH_4NO_3) in 60% ethanolic medium was recorded from 400 $m\mu$ to 720 $m\mu$. The absorption curves are all alike with the maximum at 660–670 $m\mu$, indicating formation of only one coloured complex under the conditions employed.

Composition of Complex.

Modified Mole Ratio Method : Two sets of solutions with varying moles of Fe^{3+} per mole of reagent (1 : 0.2 to 1 : 6) were prepared using fixed volume of $7.2 \times 10^{-4} M$ and $1.08 \times 10^{-3} M$ reagent (total vol., 25 ml. with 60% ethanol), and absorbances were measured at 680 $m\mu$ filter, pH 3, $\mu = 0.6$ (NH_4NO_3) and temperature 30° . The two curves (absorbance vs. moles of Fe^{3+} /moles of reagent) have sharp breaks at 1 : 1 mole ratio, giving Fe^{3+} : reagent composition 1 : 1 for the complex.

By plotting log absorbance vs. log concn. Fe^{3+} (reagent constant) using data obtained above, a linear curve having a slope 1.04 is obtained, giving 1 : 1 composition for the complex. The same composition is indicated when values of log absorbance are plotted vs. log reagent concn. (Fe^{3+} constant) as a linear curve with a slope 0.956 is obtained.

Slope Ratio Method : Two sets of solutions with 0.5 to 4.0 ml. of $3.45 \times 10^{-2} M$ variable component (Fe^{3+} or reagent) added to 5.0 ml. of $3.45 \times 10^{-2} M$ ion variable component (reagent or Fe^{3+}) were prepared with pH 2.95–3.1, $\mu = 0.6$ (NH_4NO_3), 60–40 ethanol-water, total vol. 25 ml. Plots of absorbance (680 $m\mu$ filter) vs. vol. of variable component give two practically parallel straight lines with ratio of slopes 1 : 1. Absorbances using 610 $m\mu$ filter give similar result. 1 : 1 composition is indicated accordingly for the Fe^{3+} complex.

Job's Method : Two sets of equimolar solutions ($3.55 \times 10^{-2} M$ and $6.9 \times 10^{-2} M$) of Fe^{3+} and reagent were mixed in varying proportions keeping Fe^{3+} + reagent constant (5 ml.), final vol. 25 ml., pH 2.95–3.1 and 60% ethanolic medium. Absorbances obtained at 680 $m\mu$ at 30° when plotted against vol. of Fe^{3+} give two curves with maxima at 2.5 ml. Fe^{3+} , indicating the formation of 1 : 1 complex. Job's curve for absorbances at 610 $m\mu$ filter (using $6.9 \times 10^{-2} M$ solutions) again gives a maximum at 2.5 ml. Fe^{3+} confirming the 1 : 1 composition.

Conductometric Method : Conductances of 25.0 ml. of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $0.75 \times 10^{-3} M$ reagent to which varying volumes of ten times concentrated Fe^{3+} solutions ($1 \times 10^{-2} M$ and $0.75 \times 10^{-2} M$ respectively) were added (temp. $26^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$), were measured. By plotting these

8. Vosburgh and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437.

values against volume of Fe^{3+} , curves with two straight lines intersecting at 2.5 ml. of Fe^{3+} are obtained, giving 1 : 1 molar ratio of reagent to Fe^{3+} , confirming the composition of the complex obtained by colorimetric methods.

On the basis of the 1 : 1 composition of Fe^{3+} complex obtained by above methods, the complex species formed by Fe^{3+} with 2-PRONAPOX oxime ($\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}$) in 60% ethanolic medium may be represented as $[\text{Fe}.\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}]^{++}$. In the absence of other physical evidence no formal structure for the complex is proposed here.

Authors wish to express their sincere thanks to Prof. B. C. Haldar, Head of the Department of Chemistry for his useful suggestions.

Inorganic and Nuclear
Chemistry Laboratory,
Institute of Science,
Bombay-32.

Received July 16, 1968.